

DEVELOPMENT OF MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR GAS COMPRESSOR STATIONS

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Abstract

A gas compressor station is a station whose main task is to increase the pressure of natural gas. This is done both during its production and during transportation and storage. At the same time, it is necessary to constantly maintain a given value of the discharge pressure, taking into account the main parameters that affect the operation of the compressor of the unit.

Thus, it should be noted that the topic of creating control systems for compressor units is relevant today. As is known, one of the initial stages of an optimal control system is the construction of a mathematical model based on the identification problem of a technological object. In the presented article comprehensively examines the gas compressor, which is the main technological device of a gas compressor station, as a control object. A mathematical model is constructed for the operating parameters of the compressor for gas compressor station.

Keywords: gas compressor station, device, regression equation, mathematical model, adequacy

Introduction

A gas compressor station is a whole complex of various devices, structures and equipment that are used in the extraction, storage and transportation of natural gas to the consumer. It can be said that such a station becomes the main component of the main gas pipeline. It should be noted that such important characteristics of a compressor station as efficiency and reliability directly depend on the quality of the equipment, or more precisely on their fault tolerance [1].

One of the main equipment of a gas compressor station is a piston compressor, the task of which is to move natural gas and increase its pressure. In the cylinder, the volume of natural gas is changed by means of a special device called a differential piston. Such a piston makes a reciprocating motion directly in the cavity of the cylinder itself using a crank mechanism. The principle of operation of this mechanism is based on the transformation of the rotational motion of the engine shaft into the final reciprocating motion of the differential piston [2].

Power failure – may cause a complete shutdown of all available electric motors. In this case, the emergency diesel generator will be started automatically – in order to provide the station with electricity. This generator is not capable of providing the entire gas compressor station with electricity, but it is enough to start just one gas turbine, which will maintain the operating mode.

During operation of a gas compressor station, the air in the room may heat up due to heat emission from gas turbine engines and compressors. In addition to heat emission, the air in the room is polluted with harmful gases, various combustion products, and saturated with oil vapors. Such significant heat emission, as well as air pollution and saturation with harmful components, have a detrimental effect on the health of operators. In order to prevent significant heat emission, thermal insulation is used, which covers all surfaces of equipment that emit heat.

To build control system for a certain production, first of all it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive analysis of all controlled and regulated objects located in this production. In this case, it is necessary to build a mathematical model of the control object, by means of which all aspects of interest to us, all properties of the real object are studied.

Before building a model of a real object, it is necessary to collect data on the processes occurring at the control object. There are two methods of collecting data - active and passive. The active method involves applying a control signal to the input of the control object. This control signal is a binary signal, or a step or rectangular pulse. The advantages of this method of collecting data are the highest accuracy of the resulting mathematical description, as well as the relatively short duration of the experiment. The passive method does not involve applying any control test signals, and all data on the process are obtained during normal operation of the object. The accuracy of the mathematical description will not be very high. Due to the fact that an automatic control system is used at the object, the relationship between the input and output of the object will be carried out by means of a regulator, which also leads to a decrease in the accuracy of the resulting mathematical description. In order to improve accuracy, it is necessary to accumulate a large array of data on the process, which can be considered a disadvantage of this method.

Solving of the problem

When modeling a process object, a "black box" model is used, where all input and output parameters are determined and the relationship between them is established [3].

Construction of a mathematical model of a compressor is a whole complex of actions aimed at a comprehensive study of the compressor, or the phenomena and processes occurring inside it on the model by reproducing all these processes while preserving the relationships between them and their structure.

The main feature in mathematical modeling of a compressor is the continuous reproduction of all changes in its parameters, as well as changes in the dynamics of the movement of the distribution and working bodies by calculating on a computer a sequence of numbers that express these same compressor parameters.

Before building a mathematical model of the compressor it is necessary to determine its main parameters: $X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_n$, where

X_1 - is the gas pressure at the compressor inlet
 X_2 - is the gas temperature at the compressor inlet
 X_3 - is the gas flow rate at the compressor inlet
 X_4 - the motor speed
 X_5 - is the required power

Having the specified parameters at the input, we will show a schematic model of a gas compressor unit (Fig. 1).

Fig.1 Structural diagram of the compressor of the gas compressor unit

The regression equation for the compressor will take like this [4,5]:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5.$$

$$b_0 = -45,4701; b_1 = 2,163585; b_2 = 0,106796; b_3 = 0,0000668;$$

$$b_4 = 0,007829011; b_5 = -0,00055.$$

After writing the compressor parameter values in MS Excel (table 1) and performing the calculations, we obtain the following coefficient values:

In this case, our regression equation will take form:

$$Y = -45,4701 + 2,163585X_1 + 0,106796X_2 + 0,0000668X_3 + 0,007829011X_4 - 0,00055X_5.$$

Primary statistic data

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	y
2	11,5	20	15378	7655	7702	37
3	11,6	22,5	16794	7624	8380	38,1
4	11,7	21	14457	7593	8067	37,5
5	11,8	24,6	17903	7562	9128	39,1
6	11,9	25,7	15347	7531	8793	36,3
7	12,1	29,7	17876	7500	7956	39,3
8	12,2	24,8	14682	7469	9378	38,8
9	12,3	23,5	16497	7438	9045	36
10	12,4	21,1	17103	7407	8278	40,1
11	12,5	21,3	14983	7376	9632	39,5
12	12,6	22,9	17308	7345	8853	37,1
13	12,7	28,6	17995	7314	9752	39,7
14	12,8	30	16234	7283	9474	36,9
15	12,9	29,8	15678	7252	8671	38,7
16	13,1	26,1	17245	7221	9704	36,5
17	13,2	28,4	14564	7190	8123	40
18	13,3	27,9	17569	7159	9567	39,9
19	13,4	22,3	16643	7128	8904	37,9
20	13,5	21,2	15603	7097	7890	39,2
21	13,6	27,4	14507	7066	9336	38,2
22	13,7	28,3	14783	7035	8457	39,8
23	13,8	20,6	17090	7004	9417	36,8
24	13,9	22,8	16356	6973	7913	39
25	14,1	26,5	15903	6942	8837	36,6

To check the obtained model according to Fisher's criterion, we will use the "data analysis" function of the MS Excel program (table 2).

Table 2

Checking the adequacy of the constructed model using Fisher's criterion

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	
1	ВЫВОД ИТОГОВ									
2										
3	<i>Дисперсионная статистика</i>									
4	Множест	0,9474221								
5	R-квадрат	0,8720702								
6	Нормиро	0,8586546								
7	Стандарт	1,3354664								
8	Наблюд	27								
9										
10	<i>Дисперсионный анализ</i>									
11		<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>значимость F</i>				
12	Регрессия	5	5,141193	1,028239	15,85272	8,31E-06				
13	Остаток	21	37,45288	1,783471						
14	Итого	26	42,59407							
15										
16	<i>Коэффициент корреляции</i>									
17	Y-пересеч	-45,4701	247,1567	-0,29185	0,773266	-586,123	441,8581	-586,123	441,8581	
18	Перемен	2,163585	6,42817	0,441806	0,663145	-10,5281	16,20812	-10,5281	16,20812	
19	Перемен	0,106796	0,088291	0,981831	0,33736	-0,09692	0,270298	-0,09692	0,270298	
20	Перемен	0,0000668	0,000233	0,204225	0,840144	-0,00044	0,000532	-0,00044	0,000532	
21	Перемен	0,007829	0,022885	0,461675	0,649061	-0,03703	0,058157	-0,03703	0,058157	

Conclusion

In this paper, linear mathematical model is developed, which is mainly determined as a description of the operation of gas compressor device within the regulatory limits, mainly by studying the gas compressor apparatus of the gas compressor station as a control object and taking into account its specific characteristics, in order to build a mathematical model of this technological process. The adequacy of the obtained model is determined.

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